

**“GROWTH DYNAMICS OF MUNG BEAN VARIETIES
SOWN AT DIFFERENT TIMES AND SEEDING RATES
UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF GROWTH
STIMULATORS.”**

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ABSTRACT

The effects of different sowing dates and seeding rates on the growth dynamics of mung bean varieties were studied. During the experiment, plant growth increments were determined according to their developmental stages. The highest values were recorded for the June 30 sowing date at a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare. It was observed that increasing the seeding rate improved growth up to a certain threshold; however, at higher plant densities, competition among plants intensified, leading to growth suppression. In the late sowing (July 15) treatments, reduced stem growth was observed.

Introduction: The activity of nodule bacteria plays a particularly important role in the cultivation of grain legumes. These microorganisms colonize plant roots and assimilate atmospheric free nitrogen, enriching the soil with organic matter and nitrogen, which significantly enhances plant growth and productivity. At the same time, nodule bacteria play a crucial role in maintaining soil fertility in leguminous crops such as mung bean and in creating a favorable environment for subsequent crops. This is one of the key factors for agronomists and farmers in improving yield and ensuring the efficient use of soil resources.

According to the study conducted by Sh. Ernazarov and S. Negmatova, in the foothill plains of the Qashqadaryo Region, on typical sierozem soils, sowing mung bean after winter wheat as a second crop in early July at a rate of 400 thousand viable seeds per hectare was found to be economically effective. This approach increased land-use efficiency and yield, while also playing an important role in maintaining the natural fertility of the soil [4; pp. 27–28].

In the studies conducted by Ya. Bo'riev, it was determined that cultivating mung bean as a secondary crop after winter wheat stubble has high agronomic and economic efficiency. Under optimal agronomic practices and water-limited conditions, mung bean grain yield reached 18.6–19.3 centners per hectare. In addition, the accumulation of natural nitrogen in the soil increased, creating a favorable nutrient environment for subsequent crops.

The experiments recommended cultivating the field to a depth of 18–20 cm, applying 40 kg/ha of nitrogen, 60–80 kg/ha of phosphorus, and 40–60 kg/ha of potassium fertilizers, and conducting sowing in late June–early July with 60 cm row spacing at a seeding rate of 18–20 kg/ha. During the growing season, 2–3 irrigations along with additional nitrogen application resulted in yields of 17.4 centners/ha of grain and 53.9 centners/ha of hay [1; pp. 256–257].

In studies conducted by Yu. Kenjaev and R. Oripov [2; pp. 33–36] under the conditions of the Samarkand Region, it was found that sowing 400 thousand viable mung bean seeds per hectare on lands vacated after winter wheat in early July and incorporating the resulting green biomass into the soil improved soil fertility, increased cotton yield, and enhanced fiber quality.

Additionally, mung bean, barley, rye, rapeseed, pea, and soybean were cultivated as secondary crops after cereals, producing 11.6–36.2 tons of green biomass per hectare. Incorporation of this biomass into the soil improved its agrophysical, chemical, and biological properties, which significantly increased subsequent cotton yield and fiber quality.

In experiments conducted by N. Ravshanova [3; pp. 17–18] under the conditions of the Samarkand Region, the *Pobeda-104* variety of mung bean produced a yield of 9.1 centners per hectare when sown at a spacing of 45 × 12 cm with a seeding rate of 185.2 thousand seeds per hectare.

At the same time, it was observed that with increasing plant density, stem height increased, while the number of pods, seeds, leaves, and root nodules decreased. This indicates that the proper selection of optimal seeding rates and row spacing is an important agronomic factor in ensuring yield.

One of the key indicators determining plant productivity is the level of development of vegetative organs, among which stem height is of particular importance. The stem serves as the main structural support and conduit for transporting photosynthetic products to the reproductive organs.

When stem height corresponds to varietal norms, it indicates the full expression of the plant's biological characteristics and its good adaptation to environmental conditions. Therefore, stem height is considered one of the important factors in yield formation.

In the conducted experiment, the effect of different sowing dates and seeding rates on the stem growth dynamics of the *Mahsuldor* variety of mung bean was studied. Measurements were carried out at the branching, flowering, and pod formation stages.

The obtained data showed that in all treatments, stem height increased consistently throughout the developmental stages. In the first treatment, sown on June 30 at a rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height reached 22.3 cm at the branching stage, 43.3 cm at flowering, and 69.4 cm at the pod formation stage. In the second treatment with the same seeding rate, the values were slightly higher, reaching 23.6, 45.8, and 73.2 cm, respectively.

Differences in stem growth were observed depending on the seeding rate. In the third treatment with a rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height reached 24.1 cm at the branching stage, 47.8 cm at flowering, and 77.5 cm at the pod formation stage, showing the highest values across all growth stages.

In the fourth treatment with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height was 23.9 cm at branching, 46.7 cm at flowering, and 74.1 cm at the pod formation stage, which was slightly lower than in the 300 thousand treatment. This can be explained by increased competition among plants for nutrients and light under higher plant density.

In all treatments sown on July 15, stem growth decreased compared to the June 30 sowing date. For example, in the fifth treatment with a seeding rate of 230 thousand seeds per

hectare, stem height was 21.1 cm at the branching stage, 40.5 cm at flowering, and 64.0 cm at the pod formation stage.

Table 1

**Stem growth dynamics of the mahsuldor mung bean variety, cm
(per plant; three-year average, 2022)**

№	Sowing Date	Seeding Rate (thousand seeds/ha)	Growth Stages		
			Branching stage	Flowering stage	Pod formation stage
1	June 30	230	22,3	43,3	69,4
2		230	23,6	45,8	73,2
3		300	24,1	47,8	77,5
4		400	23,9	46,7	74,1
5	July 15	230	21,1	40,5	64,0
6		230	22,4	43,0	68,3
7		300	23,1	45,0	72,0
8		400	22,7	44,0	69,5

In the sixth treatment with the same seeding rate, the values reached 22.4, 43.0, and 68.3 cm, respectively. In the seventh treatment, sown at a rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare, stem growth was relatively better, with values of 23.1 cm at the branching stage, 45.0 cm at flowering, and 72.0 cm at the pod formation stage.

In the eighth treatment, with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height was 22.7, 44.0, and 69.5 cm, respectively. Here as well, the most optimal results were observed at the seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare.

In our scientific studies, when the *Durdona* variety of mung bean was sown on June 30, the first treatment with a seeding rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare showed a stem height of 23.2 cm at the branching stage, 44.5 cm at flowering, and 71.0 cm at the pod formation stage.

In the second treatment with the same seeding rate, the values were even higher, reaching 24.1, 46.8, and 74.5 cm, respectively.

Table 2

**Stem Growth Dynamics of the *Durdona* Mung Bean Variety, cm
(per plant; three-year average, 2022)**

№	Sowing Date	Seeding Rate (thousand seeds/ha)	Growth Stages		
			Branching stage	Flowering stage	Pod formation stage

1	June 30	230	23,2	44,5	71,0
2		230	24,1	46,8	74,5
3		300	25,0	49,0	79,0
4		400	24,5	47,6	76,0
5	July 15	230	22,0	41,8	66,5
6		230	23,0	44,2	70,0
7		300	24,0	46,5	74,0
8		400	23,5	45,5	71,5

In the third treatment, with a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare, stem growth was expressed at the highest level, reaching 25.0 cm at the branching stage, 49.0 cm at flowering, and 79.0 cm at the pod formation stage. This treatment provided the maximum values across all growth stages.

In the fourth treatment, with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height was 24.5, 47.6, and 76.0 cm, respectively, showing a slight decrease compared to the 300 thousand treatment. This can be explained by increased competition among plants for light, moisture, and nutrients under higher plant density.

When sowing was carried out on July 15, stem growth in all treatments was lower compared to the June 30 sowing date. In particular, in the fifth treatment, sown at a rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height reached 22.0 cm at the branching stage, 41.8 cm at flowering, and 66.5 cm at the pod formation stage.

In the sixth treatment with the same seeding rate, the values were 23.0, 44.2, and 70.0 cm, respectively. In the seventh treatment, with a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare, stem growth was relatively more intensive, reaching 24.0 cm at the branching stage, 46.5 cm at flowering, and 74.0 cm at the pod formation stage.

In the eighth treatment, with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height was 23.5, 45.5, and 71.5 cm, respectively. Here as well, the most optimal results were observed at the seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare.

Table 3

**Stem Height of the *Mahsuldo* Mung Bean Variety by Years, cm
(per plant)**

№	Variety Name	Sowing Date	Seedin	202		
			g Rate (thousand seeds/ha)	2 y	3 y	4 y
1	Control	June 30	230	69,4	67,5	72,0
2	Mahsuldo r		230	73,2	71,5	76,0
3			300	77,5	75,1	80,0
4			400	74,1	72,3	77,5
5	Control	July 15	230	64,0	62,0	67,0
6	Mahsuldo		230	68,3	66,0	71,0

7	r		300	72,0	70,1	76,0
8			400	69,5	67,5	73,3

In the experiment, the stem height of the *Mahsuldor* variety varied depending on the sowing date and seeding rate. In the treatment sown on June 30 at a rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height was 69.4 cm in 2022, 67.5 cm in 2023, and 72.0 cm in 2024, indicating stable growth under lower seeding rates.

In another treatment with the same seeding rate, stem height ranged between 73.2 and 76.0 cm, demonstrating a relatively higher growth dynamics across the years. The treatment with a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare showed the highest stem growth, reaching 77.5 cm in 2022, 75.1 cm in 2023, and 80.0 cm in 2024, and was considered the most effective in terms of both growth and developmental stability.

In the treatment with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height ranged from 74.1 to 77.5 cm, which was slightly lower compared to the 300 thousand seeds per hectare treatment, indicating that higher plant density may sometimes limit growth.

In the late-sown treatments (July 15), stem growth was generally lower and depended on both sowing date and seeding rate. In the treatment with a seeding rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height reached 64.0 cm in 2022, 62.0 cm in 2023, and 67.0 cm in 2024, indicating relatively low growth with interannual variations of around 5 cm.

In another *Mahsuldor* treatment with the same seeding rate, stem height ranged from 68.3 to 71.0 cm, showing lower growth compared to the June 30 sowing. In the treatment with a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height ranged between 72.0 and 76.0 cm, providing stable and effective results.

In the treatment with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height ranged from 69.5 to 73.3 cm, which was lower than in the 300 thousand seeds per hectare treatment. This can be explained by increased competition among plants under higher density.

The analysis of stem height in the *Durdona* variety showed that in the June 30 sowing, the control treatment with a seeding rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare had stem heights of 71.0 cm in 2022, 69.0 cm in 2023, and 74.0 cm in 2024, indicating stable growth (with interannual variation of about 5 cm).

In the *Mahsuldor* treatment with the same seeding rate (230 thousand seeds per hectare), stem height ranged from 74.5 to 78.0 cm, demonstrating relatively higher growth performance. The treatment with a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare showed the highest stem growth, reaching 79.0 cm in 2022, 77.5 cm in 2023, and 82.5 cm in 2024, and was considered the most effective in terms of both growth and developmental stability.

In the treatment with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height ranged from 76.0 to 79.5 cm, which was lower compared to the 300 thousand seeds per hectare treatment, indicating that higher plant density may limit growth to some extent.

Table 4

Stem Height of the *Durdona* Mung Bean Variety by Years, cm

(per plant)

№	Variety Name	Sowin g Date	Seedin g Rate	202	202	202
				2 y	3 y	4 y

			(thousand seeds/ha)				
1	Control	30	June	230	71,0	69,0	74,0
2	Mahsuldo			230	74,5	73,0	78,0
3				300	79,0	77,5	82,5
4				400	76,0	74,0	79,5
5	Control	15	Jule	230	66,5	64,0	69,0
6	Mahsuldo			230	70,0	68,0	73,0
7				300	74,0	72,0	78,0
8				400	71,5	69,5	75,0

Conclusion: In the treatment sown on July 15 with a seeding rate of 230 thousand seeds per hectare (control), stem height reached 66.5 cm in 2022, 64.0 cm in 2023, and 69.0 cm in 2024, indicating generally lower growth in the late-sown variant.

In the *Mahsuldor* treatment with the same seeding rate (230 thousand seeds per hectare), stem height ranged from 70.0 to 73.0 cm, which was lower compared to the June 30 sowing, although growth stability was maintained. In the treatment with a seeding rate of 300 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height ranged from 74.0 to 78.0 cm, showing stable and effective results.

In the treatment with a seeding rate of 400 thousand seeds per hectare, stem height ranged from 71.5 to 75.0 cm, which was lower compared to the 300 thousand seeds per hectare treatment, likely due to increased competition for resources among plants at higher density.

List of references:

1. Bo'riev, Ya. Cultivation of Mung Bean in Crop Rotation Systems // Water- and Resource-Saving Agrotechnologies in Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2006, pp. 256–257.
2. Kenjaev, Yu., Oripov, R. Growth and Development Characteristics of Secondary Crops Sown after Cereals // The Role of Young Scientists in the Development of Agriculture in Uzbekistan. Samarkand, 2007, pp. 33–36
3. Ravshanova, N.A., Khalilov, N.Kh. Growth, Development, and Yield of Mung Bean Depending on Seeding Rate and Plant Density // Journal of Agriculture of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2008, No. 2, pp. 17–18.
4. Ernazarov, Sh., Negmatova, S. Yield and Efficiency of Mung Bean Cultivated on Stubble Fields // “Agro Ilm” (Scientific Supplement to the Journal of Agriculture of Uzbekistan). Tashkent, 2009, No. 1 (9), pp. 27–28